

Studies on the Decompositions and Reactions of Urea.

Part II. Reactions of Urea with Acids, Anhydrides, etc.

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As a typical case of the reaction of urea with an acid, may be discussed its action on acetic acid at the boiling point of the latter. When urea is boiled with the acid with a few crystals of silver nitrate for a short time, a precipitate of silver cyanate (which can be tested by the hydroxylamine hydrochloride-ferric chloride reaction) is formed. No silver cyanate is formed on adding silver nitrate solution at the end of the reaction. This shows that cyanic acid, which is produced under such condition, immediately reacts with the acid thus,

while the ammonia produced forms ammonium acetate. Evolution of CO_2 has been noticed to be continuous from the very outset. That, besides acetamide, ammonium salt is also formed may be easily seen by cooling a part of the mixture and adding alkali, when ammonia is evolved. Aromatic monobasic acids, however, do not yield the corresponding amides under similar conditions. Formation of imides in the case of dibasic aromatic acids is probably due to dehydrating action of cyanic acid whereby corresponding anhydrides are formed first, which latter then react with ammonia and excess of isocyanic acid thus:

The results obtained by Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1120) in the case of acetic anhydride, while supporting the above

scheme, would show that the formation of the imide on the line of Piuti (*Annalen*, 1882, 214, 20) and Dunlop (*Amer. Chem. J.*; 1896, 18, 332) may take place only to a small extent under the studied conditions.

Formation of an ureide in the case of cinnamic acid appears to be exceptional.

Esters and amides have been found to remain unreacted by urea at high temperature (150°-180°), without yielding amides and ureides respectively with the ammonia and isocyanic acid produced. But urea regarded as an amide (carbamide) yields, when heated alone, about 20% biuret thus,

Several reactions of urea in aqueous solution have been studied. It is interesting to study and compare its reactions in other solvents, *e. g.*, alcohol, glycerol and acetic acid, in which similar decomposition into ammonia and isocyanic acid have already been noticed. The temperature at which the dissociation takes place to an appreciable extent depends on the solvent. In the case of alcohol, it is approximately 82°, in the case of glycerol 100°, in the case of acetic acid 110° and in the case of water 80-85°. Since alcohol increases the rate of formation of ammonium cyanate into urea, urea is very little decomposed at its boiling point; hence very poor yields are obtained in such solution.

The reactions of urea with various bases in acetic acid solution are usually supposed to be due to the direct elimination of two molecules of ammonia from one molecule of urea and two of the base. The fact that urea dissociates into ammonia and isocyanic acid in acetic acid solution and also that phenylurea alone decomposes in the same solvent into diphenylurea, makes it more probable that the above reaction takes place thus,

Phenylurea, thus formed, then decomposes into phenyl isocyanate and ammonia (Davis and Underwood, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 2595) which then combine to form diphenylurea.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reactions of Acids and Anhydrides with Urea.

In most of these reactions, the mixtures are heated at 150-170° and then cooled and washed with small amounts of water. The residue is washed with dilute ammonia or alkali. The aliphatic imides are either extracted with some solvents or recovered by distillation. Aromatic imides are obtained in practically pure state by simply washing with dilute ammonia or alkali. Excess of urea is used in most of the cases, while with lesser amounts some of the acids or anhydrides remain unreacted. Relative proportions of the ammonium salts and amides formed also depend to some extent on the amount of urea used and also on the temperature and duration of heating. The results have been shown in Tables I—III.

Decomposition of phenylurea in acetic acid solution.—A mixture of phenylurea (1 g.) and glacial acetic acid (5-6 c. c.) was gently refluxed for about 1 hour. It was next cooled and diluted with water, when a crystalline precipitate of diphenylurea separated out. On recrystallisation from alcohol, it melted at 235°. (Found: N, 13·0. $C_{13}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 13·2 per cent).

Reactions of urea in various solvents.—Reactions of urea in glycerol were carried at 120°, in acetic acid at 117°, in water at 95-100° (except where stated), usually for 2 hours and in alcohol at 82° for 5 hours. Yields in 50% alcoholic solution were always greater than in 95% alcohol but these were small in both cases. The products were obtained by distilling off the alcohol under reduced pressure. From glycerol and acetic acid solutions, these were separated by diluting with water and proceeding in the usual way. The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE I.

Reactions of Monobasic Acids with Urea.

(A = Acid used; U = Urea).

Acid used.	Reaction and isolation.	Products formed.	M.p. and mixed m.p.	Remarks and analysis.
Acetic acid ...	A (5 g.) + U (5 g.), refluxed for 2 hours and then distilled	Acetamide, ammonium acetate	82°	Little ammonium acetate also collects in the condenser. CO ₂ is given out. Yield of the amide 30%.
Propionic acid ...	A (7.2g.) + U (6 g.) refluxed for 2½ hours and then distilled	Propionamide, ammonium propionate	79°	Distillate above 170° collected.
Phenylacetic acid ...	A (1.4g.) + U (6 g.), heated at 150°-160° for 1½ hours	Phenylacetamide, ammonium phenylacetate	156°	Yield of amide 50%.
Cinnamic acid ...	A (4g.) + U (1g.), heated at 160°-170° for 1-1½ hours	Cinnamoyl urea, ammonium cinnamate	218°-19°	(Found : C, 62.8; H, 5.11; N, 14.5. Calc. C, 63.16; H, 5.26; N, 14.73%). Crystallised from alcohol as shining flakes, yield 0.5g.
Benzoic acid ...	Heated at 150° or 170° with different proportions of urea	Ammonium benzoate		No benzamide formed. Small amount of ammonium benzoate collected in the cooler part when excess of acid is used. Benzoic acid is obtained on acidifying the filtrate.
Salicylic acid ...	A (2.6g.) + U (1.2g), heated at 150°-160° for 2 hours	Ammonium salicylate		No amide formed. Salicylic acid obtained by acidifying the filtrate.

TABLE II.

Reactions of Dibasic Acids with Urea.

(A = Acid used; U = Urea).

Acid used.	Reaction and isolation.	Products formed:	M.p. and mixed m.p.	Remarks and analysis.
Oxalic acid. (crystallised)	A (2.4g.) + U (2.4g.), heated at 150°.160° for 1½ hours, treated with water and dilute ammonia.	Oxamide	Does not melt below 270°	Ammonium salt is also formed in this and the following cases. CO ₂ is evolved.
Succinic acid	A (2.2g.) + U (2.4g.), heated as above. Imide extracted with acetone and purified from; benzene amide obtained by treating the mass with water.	Succinimide	126°	A better yield of the imide obtained by distilling the mixture.
		Succinamide	242°	
Methylsuccinic acid.	A (2g.) + U (2.6g.), heated as above. Imide extracted with ether.	Pyrotartramide	225°	
		Pyrotartrimide	66°	
Phthalic acid	A (1.7g.) + U (1.2g.), heated at 150°.160° for 2 hours, treated with water and dilute ammonia.	Phthalimide	233°	Yield 30%
Camphoric acid	Heated as above	Camphorimide	248°	Yield 40%
Quinolinic acid	"	Quinolimide	230°	Yield 35%

TABLE III.

Reactions of Acid Anhydrides with Urea.

(A = Anhydride; U = Urea).

Anhydride used.	Reaction and isolation.	Products formed.	M.p. and mixed m p.	Remarks and analysis.
Methyl succinic anhydride.	A (1 mol.) + U (2 mols.), heated at 150° for one hour, extracted with acetone and purified with ether.	Pyrotartramide	68°	CO ₂ is freely evolved in all these cases.
Phthalic anhydride.	A (1.5 g.) + U (1.2 g.), heated at 150°–160° for 1 hour, treated with water and dilute ammonia.	Phthalimide	293°	Yield quantitative. The melting point is not raised by crystallisation from ether. Dunlop (<i>loc. cit.</i>) obtained a product melting at 227° by using smaller proportion of urea. It was probably impure phthalimide.
Camphoric anhydride.	Excess of urea used. Heated at 170° for 1 hour.	Camphorimide	248°	Yield almost quantitative.
Quinolinic anhydride.	Excess of urea used. Heated at 160° for 1 hour.	Quinolimide	230°	"
Diphenic anhydride.	Heated as above with 2 mols. of urea.	Diphenimide	219°	"

TABLE IV.
Reactions of Urea in Various Solvents.

Reactants.	Alcohol (95 %).	Alcohol (50 %).	Water.	Acetic acid.	Glycerol.	Remarks.
Aniline	No action	Phenyl and diphenylurea	Phenyl and diphenylurea	Diphenylurea	Diphenylurea	Yields are poor except in acetic acid
Aniline hydrochloride	Diphenyl urea (trace)	Diphenylurea	Diphenylurea (trace at 80-85°)	"	Phenyl and diphenyl urea	Yields much greater than in the case of free base
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Carbamido derivative	Carbamido derivative	Carbamido derivative	Mixture of carbamido derivative and carbo-di- <i>p</i> -aminobenzoic acid	Ammonium salts of <i>p</i> -aminobenzoic acid and its carbamido derivative.	
Benzoic acid	No action	Ammonium salt (partial)	Ammonium salt	No action	Ammonium salt	
Phenylacetic acid	"	"	"	"	"	No amide formed in any case
Phthalic acid	"	"	Phthalimide	Phthalimide	Ammonium salt	
Phthalic anhydride	"	"	"	"	Phthalimide	

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